

On Model-based Adhesion Control of a Vortex Climbing Robot

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Abstract— In this article, the adhesion modeling and control case of a Vortex Climbing Robot (VCR) is investigated against a surface of variable orientations. The critical adhesion force exerted from the implemented Vortex Actuator (VA) and the VCR’s achievable payload are analyzed under 3-DOF rotations of the test surface, while extracted from both geometrical analysis and dynamically-simulated numerical results. A model-based control scheme is later proposed, with the goal of achieving adhesion while the VCR remains immobilized, limiting the power consumption and compensating for disturbances (e.g. moving cables) leading to Center-of-Mass (CoM) changes. Finally, the model-based control scheme is experimentally evaluated, with the VCR prototype on a rotating and moving flat surface. The presented results support the use of the proposed methodology in climbing robots targeting inspection and maintenance of stationary surfaces (flat, curved etc.), as well as future robotic solutions operating on moving structures (e.g. ships, cranes, folding bridges).

I. INTRODUCTION

Climbing Robots (CRs) targeting inspection and maintenance tasks have been traditionally multidimensional in terms of utilized adhesion technologies and motion capabilities [1], while being tailored to match specific application scenarios, environments, surface materials and geometries [2]. Efficient handling of tools and sensors for Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) and Repair (NDR) tasks requires high payload capabilities, resulting in high adhesion requirements achieved by powerful actuators [3].

In cases of challenging surface orientations involving heavy equipment, while adding the goal of high mobility for reducing the total inspection and/or repair time, CR adhesion can quickly become non-efficient, which directly affects the CRs’ potential usability as untethered robotic solutions. Energy consumptions can either be direct (e.g. high maximum current draws of on-board Electric Ducted Fan (EDF) motors [4]–[6]) or indirect (e.g. utilization of off-board compressors for maintaining vacuum [7], [8]). In the case of EDF-based adhesion, its important advantage of not requiring contact with the target surface, which alleviates the design challenges of adhesion in cases of curved, rough or non-ferromagnetic surfaces, while increasing mobility, creates the need for maximizing its performance while effectively reducing the energy consumption.

To this goal, the authors proposed an EDF-based Vortex Actuator (VA), for investigating the potential of utilizing commercially available EDFs as adhesion actuators and optimizing their adhesion efficiency. The system provided detailed analysis on various properties such as adhesion

force, pressure distribution, current draw etc. during the VA’s operation when placed in variable distances from a surface [9]. The optimized EDF configuration was later installed in a Vortex Climbing Robot (VCR) design (Fig. 1), which was evaluated under closed-loop scenarios on a flat surface of variable inclinations and open-loop scenarios, while attached on challenging curvatures (including a full-scale Boeing 737 and a water drainage pipe) [10]. In the closed loop cases, the force control was handled via a model-free PI-based scheme with empirically tuned setpoint references. While ensuring successful adhesion in all scenarios, the need for model-based control algorithms was highlighted, which would effectively reduce the overall consumption, as well as compensating for mechanical disturbances.

In EDF and generally rotor-based CR analyses found in related literature, the main research aspect focused on the analysis of negative pressure generation [11], generated thrust [4], [5], [12], general experimental studies [13] or design approaches targeting the maximization of the adhesion

Fig. 1. Photographic stills of the VCR prototype while attached and moving under varying orientations on the surfaces of (a-h) Cranfield Boeing 737: (a-b) fuselage, (c) wing, (d) turbine engine, (e) fuselage to wing transition, and (f-h) the interior of a water drainage pipe.

*This work has received funding from the European Union’s H2020 Framework Programme under the call FET-OPEN, grant agreement No. 665238.

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performance [14], [15]. Recent work provided novel considerations and detailed presentation on the utilized hardware and software of the EDF-based CRs [16], [17], although no information was provided on adhesion modeling and control aspects. Evaluation of these recent solutions was mostly performed on flat surfaces of constant orientation (e.g. wall, ceiling), while the analyzed adhesion was constrained on that particular single-plane case [14]. In [18], force and torque models were provided for a rotor-based CR in the cases of both flat and curved surfaces, although no input was provided on closed-loop force control or the cabling effects.

The novelty of this work stems from modeling the exerted force required to achieve adhesion in the case of a VCR, regardless of surface orientation, while acting as a general methodology extendable to different adhesion control technologies. The critical adhesion force and extracted achievable payload are investigated under 3-DOF surface rotations, while synthesized from both geometrical analysis and dynamically-simulated results. The second novelty is the incorporation of the extracted model in a control scheme for achieving adhesion while remaining immobilized, limiting the power consumption and compensating for disturbances (e.g. moving cables). Finally, the model-based control scheme is experimentally evaluated on the VCR prototype under a moving and rotating flat surface, thus expanding the applicability of the proposed methodology from CRs on stationary surfaces to future solutions operating on moving structures (e.g. ships, cranes, folding bridges).

The rest of this article is structured as follows. Section II presents the VCR and its main components, while Section III analyzes the adhesion modeling of the actuation unit from a theoretical and numerical approach. In Section IV, the adhesion control scheme is synthesized and presented in detail. The experimental evaluation of the proposed scheme on the VCR prototype is presented in Section V. Finally, the concluding remarks are provided in Section VI.

II. VORTEX CLIMBING ROBOT

As presented in [10] from a conceptual design and preliminary evaluation point, the VCR was designed with the primary goal of maximizing the payload that the robot can handle by utilizing a vortex actuator for achieving adhesion, while incorporating a differential-based design for enhancing the steering capabilities on the various inclination scenarios. From a structural point and as shown in Fig. 2, an EDF is placed in the middle of the robotic structure and is supported from a ring-like 3D printed frame, connected via carbon fiber tubes that incorporate cases for two miniature load cells, which sense the force F exerted from the EDF.

The selected EDF has an inner duct diameter of 92 mm, overall weight 0.67 kg and a 12-blade fan, actuated via a brushless DC motor of 2350 W maximum power at 41000 maximum rpm, which provides a maximum free-flight thrust of 3.8 kg. A 3D-Printed customized shroud of 80 mm outer radius was implemented, following an outward curvature profile and constant shroud thickness 2 mm. The shroud was set at the optimal distance of 15 mm from the test surface, as extracted from the methodology presented in [9], which led to the capability of exerting a maximum 8 kg adhesion force.

In addition, the prototype used the Turnigy AE-100A Electronic Speed Controller (ESC), while been powered by an external power supply. Two TE Connectivity FX1901

Fig. 2. The VCR prototype with highlighted components.

button-type load cells were utilized for measuring the adhesion force, while the force data were acquired via a Phidget Bridge. The overall structure enclosure was 3D printed from Polylactide (PLA), leading to a VCR prototype of dimensions 272×288×150 mm (L×W×H) and weighting approximately 2.17 kg. Finally, the control of the EDF's operation was achieved with an Arduino Mega and via a personal computer system running LabVIEW.

III. CRITICAL ADHESION MODELING

A. Theoretical Modeling

An important step towards minimization of the power needed for keeping the VCR adhered on a test surface, will be the modeling of the critical adhesion F_C needed for achieving successful adhesion, i.e. rotational and translational equilibrium, regardless of the surface orientation.

A simplified force diagram is presented in Fig. 3. While placed on the test plane, defined by the $\{x_0, y_0\}$ axes of the idle coordination system $G_0 = \{O_0, x_0, y_0, z_0\}$, the VCR remains immobilized regardless of its adhesion force F_{VA} , given a plane reaction force equal to $F_{VA} + W$, where $W = mg$ with m its mass and g the gravitational acceleration. Changing the robot orientation by angles $\{\varphi, \theta, \psi\} = \{\text{roll, pitch, yaw}\}$ around the $\{x, y, z\}$ axes, respectively, the system

Fig. 3. Simplified force diagram in (top) idle and (bottom) rotated state.

is momentarily placed on the derived plane $\{x_1, y_1\}$ of the new coordination system $G_1 = \{O_1, x_1, y_1, z_1\}$. The aforementioned Euler rotations can be represented as:

$$R_{\psi\theta\varphi} = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi c\theta & c\psi s\theta\varphi - c\varphi s\psi & s\varphi s\psi + c\varphi c\psi s\theta \\ c\theta s\psi & c\varphi c\psi + s\varphi s\psi s\theta & c\varphi s\psi s\theta - c\psi s\varphi \\ -s\theta & c\theta s\varphi & c\varphi c\theta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

where $c\cdot$ and $s\cdot$ denote the trigonometric functions $\cos(\cdot)$ and $\sin(\cdot)$, respectively.

By defining $W_0 = [W_{x,0} \ W_{y,0} \ W_{z,0}]^T = [0 \ 0 \ -mg]^T$ as the weight vector in the idle coordination system G_0 , the resulting vector W_1 in G_1 after applying the rotation matrix $R_{\psi\theta\varphi}$ around an x - y - z post-multiplication sequence will be:

$$W_1 = R_{\psi\theta\varphi} W_0 = \begin{bmatrix} -mg(s\varphi s\psi + c\varphi c\psi s\theta) \\ mg(c\psi s\varphi - c\varphi s\psi s\theta) \\ -mgc\varphi c\theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W_{x,1} \\ W_{y,1} \\ W_{z,1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

with the negative (-) sign denoting the direction of the weight vectors in relation to the positive definition of G (Fig. 3). With $\sum F_{z_1} = 0$ and (2) yielding the reaction force in the z axis $N = F_{VA} + mgc\varphi c\theta$, the resulting friction T will be defined as:

$$T = \mu N = \mu(F_{VA} + mgc\varphi c\theta), \quad (3)$$

where μ is the static friction constant. The force equilibrium in the $\{x_1, y_1\}$ plane equates the friction T with the vector addition of $W_{x,1}$ and $W_{y,1}$. Thus, by combining $\sum F_{\{x_1, y_1\}} = 0$ with (2) and (3) we receive the theoretical model describing the critical force $F_{VA} = F_C$ needed to achieve successful adhesion:

$$F_C = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } 0 \leq \gamma \leq \gamma_C \\ mg \left(\sqrt{(s\varphi)^2 + (c\varphi s\theta)^2} / \mu - c\varphi c\theta \right) & \text{for } \gamma_C \leq \gamma \leq (360^\circ - \gamma_C) \\ 0 & \text{for } (360^\circ - \gamma_C) \leq \gamma \leq 360^\circ \end{cases}. \quad (4)$$

while being constrained at the regions where the adhesion force becomes negative, which are defined by using the l^2 -norm (i.e. Euclidean norm) of the roll and pitch angles $\gamma = \sqrt{\varphi^2 + \theta^2}$ with critical value $\gamma_C = \varphi_C = \theta_C$.

Simulation of (4) for the VCR with $m = m_0 = 2.11$ kg (unloaded mass), $g = 9.80$ m/s² and $\mu = 0.8$ (as experimentally extracted from the VCR prototype and the carbon fiber test surface utilized in section V) shows the nature of the needed force for achieving successful adhesion. Specifically, and as highlighted in Fig. 4, the critical adhesion presents a symmetrical response around the inverted surface case (point A), where it gets equal to the weight of the robot (20.7 N). The vertical surface cases (points B and C) require a larger force of approximately 25.9 N, while the maximum value of 33.5 N is reached at $\varphi = 129^\circ$ and 231° (points D and

E). Angles below the critical $\varphi_C = 38.5^\circ$ (point F) and over its complementary angle 321.5° (point G) lead to infeasible negative values and are equated to zero via (4).

Considering that this analysis is performed for zero load attached on the VCR ($m_L = 0$), (4) can provide an important estimation of the payload m_L than the robot can handle for a given critical force F_C and under different orientations:

$$m_L = \frac{F_C}{\left(\sqrt{(s\varphi)^2 + (c\varphi s\theta)^2} / \mu - c\varphi c\theta \right) g} - m_0. \quad (5)$$

where m_0 denotes the unloaded system's mass. Indicatively, by setting the maximum adhesion force of the VCR prototype, which has been experimentally measured at approximately $F_{C,max} = F_{VA,max} = 80$ N, the simulation of (5) under the aforementioned physical quantities would return the maximum permitted payload $F_{L,max}$ (Fig. 5). This analysis provides an important static map for achieving stable adhesion when placing a climbing robot under a specific orientation and for a given payload. As highlighted in Fig. 5, in the inverted case ($\varphi = 180^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$) the VCR's permitted payload reaches 6.05 kg, while in the most challenging case ($\varphi = 135^\circ$ and $\theta = 0^\circ$) the robot can manage approx. 2.98 kg. It must be noted that the maximum payload curve is ultimately limited by the critical value $m_{L,max}$ defined by the robot structure and motor torque limitations.

Fig. 4. Critical force needed for successful adhesion of the VCR on a surface of different roll and pitch inclinations.

Fig. 5. Maximum permitted payload under different surface orientations.

Lastly, given the two force measurement points $F_{S,i}$ for $i = 1, 2$, the total sensed force $F_S = \sum_{i=1}^2 F_{S,i}$ will be equal to the reaction force N . This provides a way to properly extract the applied adhesion force for different plane orientations via:

$$F_{VA} = F_S - mgc\varphi c\theta. \quad (6)$$

B. Numerical Modeling

To numerically assess the adhesion performance of the VCR, MATLAB's Simscape was utilized. The capability for a direct parameterization of a dynamic model allowed it to be iteratively simulated following a parameters map that described the virtual equivalents of the system's real-world features and requirements. To this purpose, the Simscape's Multibody Contact Forces Library was used to dynamically simulate the VCR on a test surface. A view of the simulation environment developed for the VCR design model on a flat surface is presented in Fig. 6.

The performed dynamic simulations had the VCR initially touching the test surface under variable surface orientations, defined by roll φ and pitch θ angles. An exhaustive testing was performed for all angle combinations from 0° to 360° and adhesion forces ranging from 0 to 80 N. The criteria of the VCR remaining immobilized on the surface, produced the minimum adhesion force required for every roll and pitch combination, which defines a numerical model representation $F_{C,N}(\varphi, \theta)$. Indicatively, the extracted error $e_F = F_{C,N} - F_C$ between the dynamic simulations and the results provided by the geometrical model (4), are presented in Fig. 7 for both roll and pitch angles. A near identical relationship of the two models was observed, with a slight underestimation of mean 0.3 N in the case of the static theoretical model.

Advantages of the numerical model extracted via Simscape are the incorporation of dynamic characteristics regarding the relative motions of the VCR on the surface, with the basic disadvantage of being descriptive of a specific configuration. Changes to the mass or friction constants due to cable tension and other disturbances require the reacquisition of the model via a new simulation batch, thus rendering it problematic for online use in control structures. This highlights the potential usability of the proposed static theoretical model for adhesion control.

IV. ADHESION CONTROL

The block diagram for the proposed adhesion control scheme is presented in Fig. 8. The critical adhesion F_C is calculated via (4) (denoted as G_1) in an online manner via the sensed orientation angles $\varphi, \theta \in [-\pi, \pi]$. Due to the cabling weight of the tethered VCR, a constant percentage factor is tuned to assist the adhesion and counteract CoM disturbances during operation. The required force for achieving a successful adhesion F_{ref} is calculated as $F_{ref} = K \cdot F_C$, with $K \in [1, 2]$ being the disturbance compensator gain. The error e_F is computed as the difference of the current force F_{VA} and the reference value F_{ref} , which is fed to the controller C. The signal T denotes the throttle input signal sent for the VA and it is the control effort of C, required to achieve the intended force levels with a fast and smooth response. Finally, the

Fig. 6. Overview of MATLAB's Mechanics Explorer environment built for dynamically simulating the VCR under different surface orientations.

Fig. 7. Error between the theoretical (6) and the numerically extracted force model for the case of maintaining adhesion on a surface under different roll and pitch changes.

Fig. 8. Adhesion control block diagram.

force F_S measured from the load cells is properly translated to the adhesion force F_{VA} with the use of the equation (6) (noted as G_2 in Fig. 8) via the sensed orientation (φ, θ) of the setup.

In the case of high accuracy for the G_1 and G_2 models, with absence of disturbances and CoM changes, the gain K would be rendered redundant, since the computed adhesion force would allow the VCR to remain successfully adhered and immobilized. For the tethered VCR version and for connected payload, the variable K needs to be properly tuned in order to compensate for disturbances and model inaccuracies, while ensuring successful adhesion.

For the purposes of preliminarily evaluating this control scheme, a PI structure has been selected as controller C:

$$T(t) = K_p \left(e_F(t) + \frac{1}{T_I} \int_0^t e_F(t) dt \right), \quad (7)$$

where K_P is the proportional gain and T_I the reset time in minutes. As force-throttle nonlinearities have been documented in [9], this increases the difficulty in fine-tuning the control parameters K_P , and T_I for achieving efficient control performance throughout the EDFs operating range. For this reason, a gain scheduler is appropriately incorporated in the PI control structure, which adds the ability to alter the control parameters K_P and T_I according to the active region of operation, specified by the selected manipulated value:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_P \\ T_I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{P,m} \\ T_{I,m} \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } m=1, 2, \dots, M, \quad (8)$$

with $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ denoting the active operating region and M the maximum number of regions.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Setup Components

To evaluate the control performance during dynamical changes on the orientation of the VCR and, thus, the efficiency of the geometrical modeling, an experimental setup was implemented and is presented in Fig. 9(top). The VCR was placed on a carbon fiber plate ($\mu = 0.8$) with the goal of maintaining its position without slippage or loss of

Fig. 9. (top) VCR setup for evaluating the adhesion control performance on a test plate under variable orientations, (bottom) Photographic stills displaying the VCR adhesion during manual rotations of the test surface.

adhesion, while the orientation of the system was changing.

The location and orientation of the test plate and the VCR with respect to a global coordinate system were tracked via the VICON motion capture system providing a sub-millimeter accuracy. The tracked coordinate systems are denoted as $G_p = \{O_p, x_p, y_p, z_p\}$ and $G_{VCR} = \{O_{VCR}, x_{VCR}, y_{VCR}, z_{VCR}\}$ for the plate and VCR, respectively. This provided the ability of also measuring the linear velocities of the two objects, highlighted as v_p and v_{VCR} , for further evaluating their relative linear motions and identifying slippages during experimentation.

B. Adhesion Control Performance

During this preliminary experimental evaluation, the test plate was handheld and thus manually imposed disturbances were introduced that further tested the performance of the proposed control scheme. For the presented sequence, the PI controller was fine-tuned with gain-scheduled parameters, while the parameter K was empirically tuned after iterative experiments at a constant $K = 1.3$.

Fig. 10 presents the acquired results from the performed adhesion control experiment. In the examined case, the surface was manually subjected to 3-DOF rotations, highlighted by the plotting of ϕ_{VCR} , θ_{VCR} and ψ_{VCR} angles, while the controller was generating reference forces F_{ref} via the combination of (4) and parameter K . It can be also observed that the orientation change included the disturbances imposed by the manual handling of the setup (Fig. 9(bottom)), which was also affecting F_{ref} due to the tracked angle changes.

In all examined cases, the controller managed to maintain

Fig. 10. VCR adhesion response F_{VA} under alternating (ϕ, θ, ψ) plate orientations, along with the reference force F_{ref} , plate v_{plate} and VCR v_{VCR} linear velocities, position rates of change $\{\Delta \dot{x}, \Delta \dot{y}, \Delta \dot{z}\}$ between the plate and VCR, control output throttle T , and drawn power P .

adhesion and accurately regulate the force based on the orientation of the surface, with an absolute mean error e_F of approximately 2.1 N. In addition, the controller managed to keep the VCR immobilized at all times, which was assessed via the tracked position rate of changes $\Delta \dot{k} = \{\Delta \dot{x}, \Delta \dot{y}, \Delta \dot{z}\}$, as well as the linear velocities of the plate v_p and VCR v_{VA} . No slippage was observed, despite the challenging and fast rotations and translations in all three axes simultaneously, with the relative linear velocity ΔV and position rates of change being constrained at absolute mean values lower than 0.02 and 0.001 m/s, respectively. The overall performance showed successful compensation of any cabling effect and manually-imposed disturbances during experimentation, while any recorded small increases in the aforementioned outputs were a product of inertial characteristics, measurement inaccuracies and imposed vibrations from the EDF affecting both the VCR and surface objects.

As also shown in Fig. 10, the throttle signal did not exceed 67.8 %, a value applied only during the most challenging orientations. This effectively kept the power consumption at the levels of mean 0.45 kW and maximum 1.17 kW, thus leading to a 61.5 % reduction in drawn power, when compared to the case where the adhesion force is constantly set to that maximum needed value.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this study was to investigate a Vortex Climbing Robot (VCR) from a adhesion modeling and control point, while under 3-DOF surface rotational changes. The critical adhesion force and extracted achievable payload were modeled from both theoretical analysis and dynamically-simulated numerical results, which were characterized by a very close match, thus highlighting the potential applicability of the proposed computationally inexpensive static methodology. The extracted geometrical model was incorporated in a control scheme for achieving adhesion while remaining immobilized, which was experimentally evaluated. The experimental sequence involving the VCR on a manually handled surface showed successful adhesion with absence of slippages, even in the case of fast surface rotations and translations in all three axes simultaneously. The acquired results proved the validity of the model-based reference force generation, which led to a significant reduction on the power consumption by 61.5%, while compensating for the imposed disturbances (e.g. moving cables, vibrations imposed by the EDF and manual handling). In overall, the presented methodology and evaluation acted as a steppingstone towards the VCR's deployment on both immobilized and moving surfaces for autonomous performance of inspection and repair tasks.

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